

**INVESTIGATING THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF
INTEGRATED LIQUID-COOLED HEAT SINKS AND THE
PERFORMANCE OF HEAT EXCHANGERS FOR HIGH-POWER IGBTs**

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Abstract. In this paper, the physical properties of embedded liquid-cooled heat sinks, which are a type of microchannel liquid-cooled heat sinks with a built-in vapor chamber (VC embedded heat sink), to solve the problem of thermal management for high temperature, the performance and chemical properties of the capacitive heat

exchanger were studied. First, it was compared with a VC separate heat sink and a simple microchannel heat sink under the same conditions. The experimental results showed that the VC integrated heat sink has lower thermal resistance than the VC separated heat sink, and the relatively simple microchannel heat sink can significantly improve the temperature uniformity. The effect of cooling water flow rate, temperature and inclination angle on the VC mounted heat sink was further investigated. Lowering the coolant temperature lowered the heat source temperature but did not improve temperature uniformity. The tilt angle had a significant effect on the performance of the VC installed heat sink. At an inclination angle of 60° , the operation of the heat exchanger with VC was optimal.

1. Introduction.

IGBT (Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor) modules are commonly used as power semiconductors for a wide range of applications, such as industry, automobile and renewable energy [1]. A large amount of power loss is generated during the working of high-power IGBT chips, which directly affects the reliability and stability of IGBT chips. Research has shown that IGBT can produce kilowatts of power loss during normal operation [2]. The thermal stress caused by high temperature and significant temperature gradients may cause the bond wire to be left off, the silicon chips to produce holes or cracks, and the direct copper bonded to the ceramic substrate to fracture [3], leading to the failure of the IGBT module. Good thermal management is particularly important for the IGBT module. Only by timely transferring a large amount of heat generated by the IGBT chip and improving the uniformity of the heat distribution within IGBTs, can the excessive stress inside the IGBT module be eliminated and the stability and reliability of the system be improved. With the rapid development of the MCM (Multi Chip Module) packages in the high-power density devices area, more transistors want to integrate into one package module [4,5]. Therefore, as the power of IGBTs increases and the design becomes more compact, IGBT modules experience increasingly higher internal heat flux, which makes the

thermal management of IGBT modules even more challenging. Ensure the normal operation of IGBTs, robust thermal management is necessary for the IGBT module. In traditional heat dissipation technology, the cooling limit of air-cooling heat dissipation is typically 50 W/cm² cause meeting the heat dissipation requirements of high-power IGBTs is difficult. Therefore, many scholars have investigated the thermal management and thermal analysis of IGBT. Wu et al. [6] describe an unprecedented fast and accurate approach to electro-thermal simulation of power IGBTs suitable to simulate normal as well as abnormal conditions based on an advanced physics-based PS pice model together with ANSYS/Icepak FEM thermal simulator in a closed loop. Bao et al. [7] present a new solution for packaging cooling of high-power IGBT modules, in which graphene would be used in the thin-film form on the copper-coated ceramic substrate surface. In comparison to another application scheme using graphene film on the IGBT chip, this thermal management solution can better improve the heat dissipation performance of IGBT modules. Iso and Yoshiwatari [8] have applied a phase change thermal interface material (TIM) with high heat dissipation performance to IGBT modules. It has realized IGBT modules with improved heat dissipation characteristics and reliability (thermal management) was implemented. Mitic et al. [9] removed the heat directly from the surface of the IGBT by spray cooling, and the transient electrical measurement showed that the thermal resistance between the junction and the surroundings was 0.051 K/W in the case of spray

Nomenclature	
L	Length, mm
W	Width, mm
H	Height, mm
T	Temperature, °C
q	Heat flux rate, W/m ²
k	Thermal conductivity, W/(m*K)
x	Distance from heat source, mm

C1, C2	Integration constant
Th1	Temperature of heat source 1, °C
Th2	Temperature of heat source 2, °C
Th3	Temperature of heat source 3, °C
Rhs	Heat resistance, °C/W
Th, ave	Average temperature of heat source, °C
Tw,ave	Average temperature of cooling water, °C
Q	Heat source power, W
Tin	Temperature of inlet, °C
Tout	Temperature of outlet, °C
ΔT_h	max Maximum temperature difference of heat source, °C

cooling in contrast to 0.075 K/W for direct flow convection between water and baseplate. Some researchers [10–14] have used a liquid jet impingement cooling technique to thermal manage high-power IGBTs. Studies have shown that although jet impingement has a high cooling capacity, it has problems, such as poor uniformity temperature performance, high cost, complex cooling flow redistribution, cooling loop leakage, and channel blockage. Since contact thermal resistance has a significant impact on heat dissipation, thermally conductive silicone grease is widely used as effective filling material to reduce contact thermal resistance in the thermal management of electronic components. But the IGBT power modules' thermal spread capability is very sensitive to the performance and thickness of thermal grease [15]. Many scholars have studied integrated heat sinks and heat dissipation methods for IGBT to improve its heat dissipation performance, and eliminate the influence of thermal grease and contact thermal resistance on heat sink performance. Steiner and Sittig [16] investigated the liquid cooling integrated into power modules and

demonstrated it achieve thermal resistance of 0.087 K/W. Niedernostheide et al. [17] integrated the isolation sheet and the thermal grease, which the heat sink can directly contact into the package. Results demonstrate that the contact resistance between the package die pad and the isolation could be reduced by >80%. Water-cooled microchannel heat sinks were used because they are very compact and provide high cooling capabilities [18] that can usually reach 120 W/cm² [19]. Many scholars have integrated microchannel into the IGBT heat sink. Gillot et al. [20] obtained a compact IGBT module with a high thermal performance by directly integrated the microchannel heat sinks. Wang et al. [21,22] proposed a hybrid cooling system design that combines microchannel liquid cooling and thermoelectric solid-state cooling for IGBT chip thermal management. Results demonstrate that the hybrid solid and liquid cooling is a promising thermal management solution that can eliminate >90% of the temperature non-uniformity on the IGBT chip. Liu et al. [23] compared indirect and direct liquid cooling. It is found that direct liquid cooling using a microchannel cold plate can reduce thermal resistance and heat sink size of the IGBT power module effectively. Two-phase cooling has been identified as a potential solution for the cooling of IGBT modules [24] because phase transitions transfer heat rapidly. Many scholars have studied the application of heat sinks integrated with phase change elements in IGBT. Chang et al. [25] added graphite Nano-platelets (GNPs) to paraffin to prepare a composite phase change material (PCM) and filled it in an aluminum heat sink with a cavity for thermal management of the IGBT. Results demonstrate the conductivity increased by nearly five times by the GNPs loading of 15%. Mertens et al. [26] explored three types of cooling for thermal management of IGBT: single-phase convection with water, spray cooling with air–water and spray cooling with steam-water. The results of these experiments show clear advantages of airwater spray cooling IGBTs over other cooling technologies. Lu et al. [27] used heat pipe radiators to dissipate heat for two high-power IGBT modules, with a power loss of 1750 W. The experimental results showed that when the air volume was 450 m³/h, IGBT modules

could be cooled down to 67.8 °C. Avaens et al. [28] developed a power chip module based on the flat heat pipe. Ivanova et al. [29] proposed that heat pipes could be directly integrated into the DBC structure of IGBTs to improve the heat dissipation capacity of power electronic packaging components. The purpose of introducing phase change heat transfer elements into high power IGBTs is to enhance heat transfer performance and the temperature uniformity of the heat sink. Yiyi et al. [30] developed a novel thermal management system for cooling the IGBT power module. To reduce thermal resistance and improve temperature uniformity significantly, the module is integrated with a vapor chamber-based heat sink. Through 3D finite element analysis, the results show that the system is superior to the traditional cooling solutions in cooling capacity. It demonstrated that the integrated heat sink is an effective method in eliminating contact thermal resistance. Although there have been many kinds of research on integrated heat sinks for IGBTs, there is a lack of systematic comparison of the performance of various integrated heat sinks, as well as research on some parameters that should be paid attention to in the actual use of integrated heat sinks. Therefore, a microchannel liquid cooling heat sink integrated vapor chamber for high power IGBTs was developed. The manufacturing technology of the VC integrated heat sink and the wick structure of the vapor chamber were introduced. The robust comprehensive performance of the VC integrated heat sink was verified by comparing with the VC separate heat sink and simple microchannel heat sink. Besides, the effects of cooling water flow rate, temperature and inclination angle on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink were studied. The results of this study will provide key insights into how VC integrated heat sinks could be applied to the thermal management of high power IGBTs.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Design of the VC integrated heat sink This section introduces the design and manufacture of VC integrated heat sinks. The structure of the three heat sinks is shown in Fig. 1. The main differences between the VC integrated heat sink and the VC

separate heat sink were the microchannel liquid cooling plate and the vapor chamber. The VC integrated heat sink was composed of a vapor chamber and a microchannel liquid cooling plate, and the vapor chamber and the microchannel liquid cooling plate designed as a single unit. The simple microchannel heat sink only contained a microchannel liquid cooling plate. IGBT chips in the three heat sinks were directly encapsulated in the vapor chamber or the liquid cooling plates. The dimensions and parameters of the heat sink are shown in Table 1.

2.2. Manufacture of the VC integrated heat sink

The manufacturing processes of the VC integrated heat sink were as follows. (1) A cavity with a depth of 4 mm was milled on a 130 mm × 72 mm × 7 mm copper plate as the cover plate of the vapor chamber. The edge of the cavity was reserved for 3 mm, and 21 circulars with a diameter of 3 mm have treated support columns. (2) Excess material on the back of the cavity was removed, and holes with a diameter of 5.5 mm in four corners were processed as installation holes. The convex plate (85 mm × 58.5 mm × 8 mm) was reserved for processing the microchannel array. (3) The microchannel array was manufactured

Fig. 1. Structure of the heat sinks.

Table 1

Dimensions and parameters of the heat sinks.	
Parameter	Value
Basement of integrated heat sink (L × W × H)/mm	130 × 72 × 7
Seal gasket (L × W × H)/mm	123 × 65 × 0.5
Heat sink cover plate (L × W × H)/mm	130 × 72 × 11
Microchannel size (L × W × H)/mm	85 × 0.5 × 8
Number of microchannel	58

wire-EDM, since a fine quality microchannel can be obtained by a micro wire-EDM mechanism [31], and the microchannel array on the back of the cover plate of

the vapor chamber can be processed by a wire EDM mechanism. The cover plate of the vapor chamber is shown in [Fig. 2. \(4\)](#) A copper plate with a thickness of 1 mm and a smooth surface was used to cut the vapor chamber basement plate (130 mm × 72 mm × 1 mm).[\(5\)](#) The wick of the VC integrated heat sink is shown in [Fig. 3\(a\)](#) and (b).

The sintered foamy copper with a thickness of 1 mm on the cover plate of the vapor chamber served as the condensation end wick ([Fig. 3\(a\)](#)), and the sintered copper powder with a thickness of 1 mm on the base plate of the vapor chamber served as the evaporation end wick ([Fig. 3\(b\)](#)). [\(6\)](#) The basement plate and the liquid injection tube were brazed to form a sealed cavity, and 10 g of deionized water was injected into the cavity as the working substance. Finally, the vapor chamber was vacuumed to reduce the pressure to less than 10 Pa, and seal the liquid injection tube to complete the integrated heat sink. In this study, the vapor chamber and microchannel liquid cooling plate of the VC separate heat sink and the simple microchannel heat sink was the same as that of the VC integrated heat sink. The VC integrated heat sink is shown in [Fig. 4](#). Different from the VC integrated heat sink, as shown in [Fig. 5](#), the VC separate heat sink is composed of a vapor chamber ([Fig. 5 \(a\)](#)) and a microchannel array ([Fig. 5 \(b\)](#)). As the channel of the working substance, the wick is the core structure of the vapor chamber. Various studies [\[32,33\]](#) have shown that

(a) Cavity of vapor chamber cover plate

(b) Microchannel array

Fig. 2. Diagram of the vapor chamber cover plate of the integrated heat sink.

(a) Foamy copper wick (b) Copper powder sintered wick

Fig. 3. Wick of the vapor chamber.

Fig. 4. Diagram of the integrated heat sink.

the heat transfer capacity of the vapor chamber can be improved by adding a porous structure in the middle of both ends of the wick. Therefore, the irregular copper powder was used to prepare the wick for the evaporation end, which had a copper sintering column with a diameter of 2 mm on the IGBT position and a copper sintering convex with a width of 2 mm on the edge of the wick (Fig. 3(b)). The function of the copper sintering column and convex was to increase the channel of the working substance.

3.Experimental methods

3.1.Experimental setup

A schematic diagram of the heat sink test platform is shown in Fig.6. It primarily includes the heating module, cooling module and data acquisition module. The heating module's function is to simulate the chip to generate heat, which primarily includes a heated copper block, six adjustable DC power supplies, heating rods as well as Bakelite and Silicone foam sponges used in adiabatic. The arrangement of heating rods under a heating copper block included an adjustable DC power supply for heating output power with a

voltage precision of 0.1% and a current accuracy of 0.5%. The main function of the cooling module is to transfer heat from cooling water to air. The cooling module includes a low-temperature thermostatic water tank (DC-0530), glass rotor flow- meter (LZB-10) and a cooling pipeline. The temperature fluctuation range of the low-temperature thermostatic water tank was ± 0.05 °C. The measuring range of the glass rotor flowmeter with four class accuracies was 10–100 L/H. The data acquisition module was to collect and record temperature and pressure data, via the temperature data acquisition instrument, T-type thermocouple, digital display manometer and

computer. The acquisition instrument can detect temperature changes >0.02 °C, and the test precision of the thermocouple was ± 0.1 °C. In the test platform, the heat sink, the heated copper block and the other parts were wrapped by a Silicone foam sponge. The thermal conductivity of the Silicone foam sponge was less than 0.3 W/(m·K), which can reduce the heat loss in the system [34–36].

Four thermocouples (T3–T6) were arranged at the bottom of the heat sink; T16 and T17 were arranged at the heat sink inlet and outlet. T_{in} and T_{out} are the temperatures of the inlet and outlet, respectively. Although the chip temperature is a crucial parameter for the thermal management of IGBTs, direct measuring the chip temperature is difficult. Thus, six rectangular copper columns with an area of 1×1 cm² were used to simulate chip heating in this study. Nine thermocouples (T7–T15) were welded on the three copper columns on the same side for temperature collection. The schematic diagram of the collected temperature is shown in Fig. 7. The heat source temperature can calculate from the temperature data obtained from the temperature collection point. The formula [37] was as follows:

$$T(x) = -\frac{q'}{2k}x + C_1x + C_2$$

where q' is the heat flux rate, k is the thermal conductivity, x is the distance from the heat source and C_1 and C_2 are the integration constants.

The six rectangular copper columns in Fig. 7 are symmetrical distribution and under the same conditions to conduct experiments. Therefore, only three of the copper columns take as research objects.

(a)vaper chamber part

(b) Mikrochannel array part

Fig. 5. The diagram of the separate heat sink.

Fig. 6. Physical diagram of the heat sink performance experimental test platform.

Fig. 7. Schematic diagram of the heating copper block temperature collection point.

According to the temperature collection point distribution on the copper column, the temperature T_{h1} of the heat source 1 could be calculated by Eq (2). Similarly, T_{h2} and T_{h3} could be calculated by Eq.3 and Eq.4, respectively.

$$T_{h1} = T_7 + 3T_8 - 3T_9 \quad (2)$$

$$T_{h2} = T_{10} + 3T_{11} - 3T_{12} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{h3} = T_{13} + 3T_{14} - 3T_{15} \quad (4)$$

Before the experiment, all samples were thoroughly cleaned with absolute ethanol and deionized water. To reduce the contact thermal resistance, a thin layer of heat-conducting silicone grease with thermal conductivity of 5.0 W/(m·K) coated between the heating copper block and the heat sink.

And use screws to fix the sample on the bakelite installed with the heat copper block to ensure good contact between the heating copper block and the sample. When testing the three heat sinks, it installed horizontally, and the cooling water temperature is 25°C. The heating module has a constant heating power of 385 W. Before testing, make sure that the thermocouples are in good contact. The experiment starts when all the thermocouple temperatures are equal to the inlet temperature. When reached to balance, it can increase the cooling water flow rate. During the test, the cooling water flow increased from 30L/H to 70L/H. Only one of the variables was changed when testing the

performance of the heat sink. Each experiment was repeated three times to reduce errors.

3.2. Performance evaluation index

Using the heat resistance of the heat sink as the evaluation index of heat dissipation performance, the calculation formula of the heat resistance of the heat sink R_{hs} [38] was as follows:

$$R_{hs} = \frac{T_{h,ave} - T_{w,ave}}{Q}$$

where $T_{h,ave}$ is the average temperature of the heat source and $T_{w,ave}$ is the average temperature of cooling water.

The average temperature of heat source $T_{h,ave}$ can be represented by the heat transfer performance of the heat sink, which can be calculated by Eq. (6)

$$T_{h,ave} = \frac{T_{h1} + T_{h2} + T_{h3}}{3}$$

The average temperature of the cooling water $T_{w,ave}$ can be calculated by Eq.(7)

$$T_{w,ave} = \frac{T_{in} + T_{out}}{2}$$

Lee [39] suggested that the temperature uniformity of the IGBT heat sink was as crucial as the heat transfer performance. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the uniformity performance of heat sinks. The maximum temperature difference of the heat source is used as the evaluation index of the temperature uniformity of the heat sink, the maximum temperature difference ΔT_{h-max} of the heat source can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\Delta T_{h-max} = \text{MAX}(T_{h1}, T_{h2}, T_{h3}) - \text{MIN}(T_{h1}, T_{h2}, T_{h3})$$

4. Results and analysis

4.1. Comparison and analysis of heat transfer performance of three heat sinks

The average temperature of heat source with VC integrated heat sink, VC

separate heat sink and simple microchannel heat sink at different cooling water flow rates is shown in Fig. 8. Although the average temperature of the heat source with the VC integrated heat sink was approximately 4 °C lower than that with the VC separate heat sink, it was approximately 7 °C higher than that with the simple microchannel heat sink. It indicated that the best heat transfer performance is the simple microchannel heat sink, followed by VC integrated heat sink, and the worst is VC separate heat sink.

4.2. Comparison and analysis of the thermal resistance of three heat sinks

The thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink, VC separate heat sink and simple microchannel heat sink at different cooling water flow rates is shown in Fig. 9. Comparing the VC integrated heat sink and VC separate heat sink, although both are composed of vapor chamber and microchannel liquid

cooling plate, the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink was approximately 0.01 °C/W lower than that of the VC separate heat sink. This difference can be explained by the contact thermal resistance between the vapor chamber and the microchannel liquid cooling plate in the VC separate heat sink.

Although the thermal silicone grease was coated during the experiment, Koorosh et al. [40] found by comparison that the contact thermal resistance was reduced by about 38% after using the Nano-coating, which indicated that the thermal silicone grease did not completely eliminate the contact thermal resistance. Moreover, VC integrated heat sink avoids the contact thermal resistance at the interface between the vapor chamber and the micro-channel

cooling plate. However, the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink is higher $0.02\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{W}$ than that of the simple microchannel heat sink. To ensure a single variable for the tested sample, the thickness of the substrate of the simple microchannel heat sink and the evaporation end of the vapor chamber is identical. Therefore, the thickness of the substrate of the simple microchannel heat sink thinner than the vapor chamber (the details are shown in Fig. 1). Although the vapor chamber of the VC integrated heat sink can quickly transfer heat, the thickness of the substrate (vapor chamber) of the VC integrated heat sink is seven times thicker than that of the simple microchannel substrate.

Fig. 9. Thermal resistance of the three heat sinks at different flow rates

Although the average temperature of the heat source (Fig. 8) and the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink are higher than that of the simple microchannel heat sink (Fig. 9), the maximum temperature difference of the heat source shows different laws. The maximum temperature difference

of the heat source with the VC integrated heat sink and the simple microchannel heat sink at different cooling water flow rates is shown in Fig. 10. The maximum temperature difference of the heat source with the simple microchannel heat sink was higher than that with the VC integrated heat sink, and the former was at least $7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ higher than the latter, which indicated that the VC integrated heat sink could greatly improve the temperature uniformity of

the heat sink. It can be seen from the above that for the application of IGBT thermal management, the VC integrated heat sink is the best performance among the three heat sinks. Considering the diverse situations of IGBT in actual use, it is necessary to investigate the performance of VC integrated heat sink under various conditions. Therefore, the following section will conduct an inquiry into the influence of some factors on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink.

4.3. Analysis of factors affecting the performance of the VC integrated heat sink

4.3.1. The influence of the inlet flow rates on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink

The temperature of the three heat sources with the VC integrated heat sink under different cooling water flows is shown in [Fig. 11](#). The temperature of the three heat sources did not exceed 70 °C. The temperatures of the three heat sources decreased as the cooling water flow increased. This pattern likely stemmed from the fact that as the cooling water flow rate increased, the flow velocity of cooling water in the microchannel also increased. The increase in the cooling water flow rate in the microchannel affected the thermal boundary layer of the micro-channel. It resulted in a gradual reduction of convective heat transfer thermal resistance and improved the heat transfer efficiency between cooling water and the microchannel wall. Although the heat source temperature gradually decreased as the cooling water flow rate increased, the trend of temperature decrease also decreased gradually because the convective thermal resistance gradually decreased with the cooling water flow rate. Besides, the temperature of the three simulated heat sources at different cooling water flow rates showed the following rank order: $T_{h1} < T_{h2} < T_{h3}$. The temperature at the inlet of the VC integrated heat sink is the lowest. In the direction from the inlet to the outlet due to convection heat transfer, there is a temperature gradient

in this direction, which causes the temperature of the heat source to gradually increase from the inlet to the outlet.

The maximum temperature difference of the VC integrated heat sink at different cooling water flow rates is shown in Fig. 12. The maximum temperature difference of the heat source increased as the cooling water flow rate increased. When the cooling water flow rate increased from 30 L/H to 70 L/H, the maximum temperature difference of the heat sources increased from 6.75 °C to 8.02 °C, an increase of 1.27 °C, which indicated that increase of the cooling water flow rate will deteriorate the temperature uniformity. That is

because, as the inlet flow rate increases, the convective heat transfer capacity of the VC integrated heat sink is enhanced. Although the heat taken away by the heat source at the inlet and outlet will increase, the temperature at the inlet is the lowest in the entire heat sink. As the inlet flow increases, the heat source temperature

Fig. 11. Source temperature at different flow rates.

Fig. 12. Maximum temperature difference of the heat source at different flow rates.

near the inlet decreases more than the heat source at the outlet, which causes the temperature difference of the heat source to increase with the increase of the inlet flow. And it can be seen from Fig. 11 that the heat source temperature T_{h1} decrease more significantly than that T_{h3} as the flow rate increases.

The relationship between the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink and the cooling water flow rate is shown in Fig. 13. The thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink decreased slowly as the cooling water flow rate increased. When the cooling water flow rate increased from 30 L/H to 70 L/H, the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink decreased from 0.087 °C/W to 0.083 °C/W, indicating that the cooling water flow rate had little influence on the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink, allowing it to be ignored.

4.3.2. The influence of the temperature of the cooling water on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink

The average temperature of heat source and thermal resistance at different cooling water temperature are shown in Fig. 14 (a) and (b), respectively. It can

be seen from Fig. 14(a) that an increase in the cooling water temperature led to increases in the average temperature of the heat source. This pattern stems from the fact that when the cooling water temperature increased, the average temperature of the heat sink will also increase. If the thermal resistance of the heat sink is constant, from

Fig. 13. Thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink at different flow rates.

Eq. (5), the average temperature of the heat source will inevitably increase by the same magnitude. Therefore, when the temperature of the cooling water rises from 25 °C to 35 °C, the average temperature of the heat source also increases by approximately 10 °C. From the Fig. 14(b), it can be seen that the thermal resistance of the heat sink decreased as the water temperature increased at the same cooling rate. It is because that the change of average temperature of heat source does not equivalent changes in the average temperature of cooling water. And the change of average temperature of cooling water is larger than that of heat source. Therefore, it can be seen from the Eq.(5) that as the cooling water temperature increase, the thermal resistance of the heat sink decreases.

(a) Average temperature of the heat source at different cooling water temperatures

(b) Thermal resistance at different cooling water temperatures

Fig. 14. Graph of the average temperature of the heat resource (a) and thermal resistance (b) of the VC integrated heat sink under different cooling water temperatures.

Therefore, it can be seen from the Eq.(5) that as the cooling water temperature increase, the thermal resistance of the heat sink decreases. The study of Chernysheva et al[41] shown that the thermal resistance of loop heat pipe(LHP) decreases with an increase in the cooling temperature. It is caused by the increase in condenser cooling temperature leads to a decrease in the temperature drop between the evaporator and the condenser. On the other hand, the steam thermal conductivity increases with the temperature [42]. The heat transfer of the vapor chamber is enhanced, resulting in a decrease in the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink.

The maximum temperature difference of the heat source under different

cooling water temperatures is shown in Fig. 15. When the cooling water flow rate was the same, higher cooling water temperatures corresponded to smaller maximum temperature differences. Thus, increasing the cooling water temperature improves the temperature uniformity of the VC integrated heat sink. This pattern can be explained by the fact that the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink decreases as cooling water temperature increases. Therefore, higher cooling water temperatures correspond to better temperature uniformity of the VC integrated heat sink. It is recommended to use higher cooling water temperatures under the premise of meeting the requirements of heat dissipation. Besides, it can be seen that the same law as in Fig. 12 is that the increase in flow rate at the same cooling water temperature will deteriorate the temperature uniformity.

Owing to the vapor chamber is the crucial part of the VC integrated heat sink, the distribution and flow of the working substance inside the vapor chamber have a significant influence on the performance of the heat sink. And the relationship between gravity and the flow direction of the working fluid significantly affects the vapor–liquid distribution and flow, and further affects the heat performance of the heat pipe [43]. Considering IGBT will be applied in different situations in actual use. The VC integrated heat sink will not always be in the horizontal state. On the other hand Ji et al. [43] compared the performance and thermal resistance changes of the integrated flat heat pipe (IFHP) and the conventional flat heat pipe (CFHP) at 0°, 90°, and 180° inclination angles. But, first of all, the structure of the heat sink is different. The research results are not suitable for any variety of heat sinks. Secondly, it only studies the performance at inclination angles of 0°, 90°, and 180°. In the actual use, it may not only be at these angles. Thus it is necessary to investigate the effects of the inclination angles on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink.

4.3.3. The influence of the inclination angle on the performance of the VC integrated heat sink

In addition to the performance of the VC integrated heat sink tested under the horizontal condition (0°), the performance under inclination angles of 30° , 60° and 90° was also tested. Fig. 16 is a schematic diagram of the inclination angle of the VC integrated heat sink.

The average temperature of the heat source and the thermal resistance of the VC integrated heat sink under different inclination angles is shown in Fig. 17. It is shown that the inclination angle has the same effect on the average temperature of the heat source and the thermal resistance. The average temperature and the thermal resistance under

the constant flow rate showed the following rank order: $0^\circ > 30^\circ > 90^\circ > 60^\circ$. It can be explained by the fact that when the VC integrated heat sink is inclined

at a certain angle, it is conducive to the circulation of the working substance inside the vapor chamber. When the inclination

Fig. 16. Schematic diagram of the inclination angle of the VC integrated heat sink.

(a) Average temperature of the heat resource under different inclination angles

(b) thermal resistance of the integrated heat sink under different inclination angles

Fig. 17. Average temperature of the heat resource (a) and thermal resistance

(b) under different inclination angles.

angle reached 90° , the VC integrated heat sink was in a vertical state. At this point, where the reflux speed of the liquid working substance at the condensing end exceeds the evaporation speed at the evaporating end, a large amount of liquid working substance accumulates in the evaporating end lead to form a thick liquid film, which is not conducive to the evaporation of the working substance and led to the deterioration of the heat transfer condition in the vapor chamber. Furthermore, Kumaresan et al. [44] studied the effect of the tilt angle on the performance of the heat pipe through experiments and found

that there is an optimal tilt angle. When the tilt angle is closer to the vertical position, the performance decreases. It is because a large tilt angle accelerates the return of the liquid working fluid lead to the function of the evaporation section is affected. Among the four inclination angles, the VC integrated heat sink with an inclination angle of 60° had the best heat dissipation performance and thermal resistance characteristics.

The maximum temperature difference of the heat source under different inclination angles is shown in [Fig. 18](#). Among the four inclination angles, the VC integrated heat sink installed at 60° had the best temperature uniformity. Besides, when the inclination angle was 30° and 60° , the temperature uniformity of the VC integrated heat sink was less affected by the cooling water flow rate, while the maximum temperature difference of the heat source under the other two inclination angles (0° and 90°) increased as the cooling water flow rate increased. When the VC integrated heat sink was inclined at 30° and 60° , it is facilitated the diffusion of the working substance steam and the condensation backflow in the VC integrated heat sink, resulting in the temperature uniformity being less affected by the cooling water flow rate.

5. Conclusions

The heat transfer performance and thermal resistance characteristics of the three kinds of heat sinks all show the same law: the best is the simple microchannel heat sink, followed by VC integrated heat sink, and the worst is the VC separate heat sink. However, the temperature uniformity of the VC integrated heat sink is better than that of the simple microchannel heat sink.

The heat source temperature with the VC integrated heat sink decreases with the increase of the cooling water flow rate. And as the flow rate increases, the temperature uniformity reduces, but it has almost no effect on the thermal resistance.

As the cooling water temperature of increases, the heat source temperature

risers, and its increment is virtually the same as the cooling water temperature. However, the higher the cooling water temperature, the more conducive to reducing the thermal resistance and enhancing the temperature uniformity.

Fig. 18. Maximum temperature difference of the heat source under different inclination angles.

When the VC integrated heat sink is at different inclination angles, the heat transfer performance, thermal resistance characteristics and temperature uniformity of the heat sink all show the same law, the order from best to worst is $60^\circ > 90^\circ > 30^\circ > 0^\circ$.

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